

Synthesis and antibacterial activity of new Schiff bases, 4-thiazolidinones and 2-azetidiones

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New Schiff bases (1a-e), 4-thiazolidinones (2a-e) and 2-azetidiones (3a-e) have been synthesized and tested for their antibacterial activity.

Schiff bases possess diversified biological applications¹. Various 4-thiazolidinones show a variety of pharmacological and microbiological activities². Moreover, compounds containing 2-azetidione ring system are shown to possess marked biological activities³. Various 4-thiazolidinones inhibit the bacterial enzyme in biosynthesis of polymers⁴. Some derivatives of 2,3-diaryl-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones have been proved to be highly effective in inhibiting HIV-1 replication at nanomolar concentration thereby acting as a non-nucleosides HIV-1 inhibitors (NNRTIs)⁵.

The present paper reports the synthesis of some new Schiff bases, 4-thiazolidinones and 2-azetidiones.

2-Hydroxy-3-iodo-5-chlorobenzaldehyde on condensation with various substituted aromatic primary amines furnished the Schiff bases **1a-e**. These compounds on condensation with mercaptoacetic acid in dioxane in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride afforded 4-thiazolidinones (**2a-e**). The Schiff bases (**1**) on reaction with chloroacetyl chloride in dioxane in the presence of triethylamine yielded 2-azetidiones (**3a-e**) (Scheme 1).

The compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity⁶ against *Escherichia coli* (EC), *Bacillus subtilis* (BS) and *Salmonella dysenterae* (SD) at 150 ppm concentration using tetracycline as standard. Compounds **1c**, **2b** and **3e** showed good antibacterial activity and the remaining compounds showed moderate to less activity.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries in a liquid paraffin bath and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

2-Hydroxy-3-iodo-5-chlorobenzylidene-(4-methoxy)-

aniline (1b): To a mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-5-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.001 mol) and *p*-anisidine (0.001 mol) dissolved in ethanol (25 ml), 1 drop of acetic acid was added and refluxed for 2 h. The content was then cooled and poured

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) EtOH, (ii) SH-CH₂-COOH/dioxane, (iii) Cl-CH₂-COCl/Et₃N.

in crushed ice. The separated solid was crystallized from ethanol, (64%), m.p. 117° (Found : C, 43.35; H, 2.83; N, 3.59. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{11}NO_2Cl$ (387.61) : C, 43.38; H, 2.86; N, 3.61%); ν_{max} 1630 (C=N) and 1590 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (CDCl₃) 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.1–7.8 (6H, m, Ar-H), 8.6 (1H, s, =CH) and 13.8 (1H, s, Ar-OH).

All other compounds (yields 69–75%) were prepared by similar procedure : **1a**, m.p. 91°; **c**, 120°; **d**, 102°, ν_{max} 1625 (C=N), 1595 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (CDCl₃) 7.1–7.8 (6H, m, ArH), 8.6 (1H, s, =CH), 13.7 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 10.5 (1H, s, COOH); **e**, 125°.

2-(2-Hydroxy, 3-iodo, 5-chlorophenyl)-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-thiazolidinone (2b) : To a mixture of **1** (0.001 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.001 mol) dissolved in dioxane (20 ml), anhyd. zinc chloride (0.5 mg) was added and refluxed for 8 h. The reaction was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallized from ethanol, (63%), m. p. 170° (Found : C, 41.60; H, 2.85; N, 3.01. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{13}NO_3S$ (461.71) : C, 41.62; H, 2.84; N, 3.03%); ν_{max} 1665 (C=O), 1580–1608 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (CDCl₃) 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.1 (2H, s, CH₂S), 6.75 (1H, s, N-CH), 7.1–8.4 (6H, m, ArH) and 13.7 (1H, s, Ar-OH).

All other compounds (yields 56–67%) were prepared by similar procedure : **2a**, m.p. 140°; **c**, 187°; **d**, 195°, ν_{max} 1660 (C=O), 2685 (O-H), 1685 (C=O), 1550–1610 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (CDCl₃) 4.7 (2H, s, CH₂S), 6.7 (1H, s, N-CH), 7.3–8.4 (6H, m, ArH), 10.8 (1H, s, COOH), 13.6 (1H, s, Ar-OH); **e**, 175°.

1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-chloro-4-(2'-hydroxy, 3'-iodo, 5'-chlorophenyl)-2-azetidinone (3b) : To a mixture of **1** (0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.003 mol) dissolved in dioxane (25 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.0012 mol) in dioxane was added dropwise at 10°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 6 h. Half of the solvent was then removed by distillation and cooled. The solid separated was crystallized from chloroform, (55%), m. p. 198° (Found : C, 41.39; H,

2.58; N, 3.00. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{12}NO_3Cl_2I$ (464.09) : C, 41.41; H, 2.61; N, 3.02%); ν_{max} 1750 (C=O), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (CDCl₃) 2.5 (1H, d, N-CH), 4.1 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.45 (1H, d, CH-Cl), 7.3–8.4 (6H, m, Ar-H) and 13.5 (1H, s, ArOH).

All other compounds (yields 60–71%) were prepared by similar procedure : **3a**, m.p. 157°; **c**, 164°; **d**, 187°, ν_{max} 1750 (C=O) and 1610 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (CDCl₃) : 2.3 (1H, d, N-CH), 4.5 (1H, d, CH-Cl), 7.1–8.0 (6H, m, ArH), 10.2 (1H, s, COOH) and 13.2 (1H, s, Ar-OH); **e**, 169°.

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